

Warpbird: an Untethered System on Chip Using RISC-V Cores and the Rocket Chip Infrastructure

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Abstract

The extraordinary infrastructure needed to operate any computer in general takes several years to develop and requires intensive capital investment. Hence, only large companies can afford to build systems using processor cores, leaving small but very innovative companies out of this game. It is possible to license processor cores from providers such as ARM but this is still too expensive for many small enterprises. This problem is slowly but effectively being addressed in the open source community by making available, free of charge, high quality hardware and software components which innovative companies can use to assemble complex systems. After a few attempts to create an open source processor and surrounding ecosystem, the RISC-V free instruction set architecture has emerged in full force and inspired a new wave of hope that the problem is finally going to be solved. This paper presents both a methodology for creating systems on chip (SoCs), using RISC-V cores, and a base open source SoC called Warpbird, which it is claimed here to be the first untethered SoC of its kind. An experimental evaluation of the open source components used and of the system itself is provided.

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

As the world becomes more interconnected, it is time for things, in addition to people, to join the cloud. The *Internet of Things*, as it is currently coined, offers a practically infinite number of possibilities for building innovative devices. A piece of semiconductor IP, which can be quickly configured to embody a device drawn from a brilliant engineer's mind, is now, more than ever, an extremely valuable asset. Differentiation normally demands that these Internet things have aggressive specifications in terms of area, performance and power consumption.

Such piece of IP is indeed an SoC. In its almost 30 years of existence, the IP market evolved from supplying small components to providing complete subsystems with one or more processors and several software components. SoCs normally contain one main IP system, responsible for top-level control, and a bunch of specialized IP subsystems.

1.2. Problem

The current situation poses a severe problem to new entrants in the semiconductor IP market. Having access to every hardware and software building block needed for a complete system is expensive and/or takes too long.

Furthermore, the available open source solutions are either dependent on a specific technology, have no parameterization options, or have non-robust development environments [1]. The available open source "SoCs" are often dependent on a specific non-free toolchain, simulator or FPGA that is used to demo their apparent capacities. However, due to a nonexistent ecosystem, these initiatives tend to fade out. Here, this problem is called the tethered SoC problem. These SoCs can hardly have an existence of their own.

1.3. Solution

The solution may be similar to the one found for Operating Systems (OS's): free open source OS's have emerged which in many aspects are better and more robust than commercial and closed source alternatives.

With the emergence of the RISC-V instruction set architecture (ISA) [2] and its open source toolchain, with special emphasis on the Chisel3 Hardware Description Language (HDL) [3] and the Rocket Chip Generator [4], it is likely that the success of open source OS's is extended to open hardware descriptions. In fact, this paper is the continuation of the work reported in [1], where an attempt to create an SoC called Blackbird, and a programming environment for building reconfigurable systems using the OpenRISC open source processor has been made.

Unfortunately, the OpenRISC initiative has failed to create a mature enough ecosystem of its own, and the effort revealed itself too onerous, as many essential parts of the system were missing and/or were still being developed by the small active community. In fact, in spite of the initial enthusiasm, the same may happen to RISC-V.

However, the recent impetus of the RISC-V initiative is far stronger than OpenRISC has ever enjoyed. Moreover, crowd development is becoming increasingly easier with the advent of code sharing platforms such as `github.com`. In this new context, this paper presents a fresh attempt to investigate the techniques used in developing Warpbird, a truly untethered SoC.

1.4. Objectives

This project has an objective to investigate whether a SoC built from open source RISC-V cores can be silicon ready and built in a time frame comparable to using commercial IP cores. To accomplish this goal, we envision the following steps:

1. build the Warbird SoC using the Rocket Chip SoC generator, which contains RISC-V cores;
2. use the Rocket Chip infrastructure to develop an environment where software and hardware components can be easily added, removed or modified;
3. build a development environment encompassing all stages of building an SoC: hardware design, software design, RTL simulation and FPGA emulation, using up to date software and hardware debug techniques.

1.5. Outline

This paper is organized as follows. In section 2, the Warbird SoC instance implemented with completely open source modules is described. Section 3 describes the verification methods used with the proposed SoC. The programming tools are described in section 4. In section 5, the development flow for Warbird is outlined. Finally, in section 6, the early-stage results of this research and its main conclusions are presented.

2. SoC design

In order to illustrate the design of an SoC using open source components, this research used Rocket Chip [4], which is an open-source design generator that emits synthesizable RTL based on general-purpose processor cores using the RISC-V ISA. Rocket Chip is composed of a set of utilities used to design and parameterize a fully functional SoC. It comes with an emulator, build and regression test environments, two RISC-V core types (in-order and out-of-order), a RISC-V toolchain to develop software, caches, and interconnects. The user describes systems and cores using Chisel3 [3] and writes its SoC configuration in the top level domain. Rocket Chip will then generate all the Verilog code needed by the design.

Other open source processors have been carefully considered, namely Leon 2 [5], LatticeMico32 [6], and OpenRISC [7]. Two decisive success factors have been identified: (1) whether there is an active community maintaining the code, and (2) whether the toolchain is comprehensive and open. Leon 2 is no longer maintained as the company that gave origin to it (Gaisler Research) has been acquired by American company Aeroflex in 2008, which in turn has merged with UK aerospace company Cobham. LatticeMico32 still lacks crucial tools such as a good debug environment, and the OpenRISC project does not have a sufficiently numerous and active community. Soft processors that are not completely open such as Microblaze and its few clones, such as the OpenFire processor [8], are not

Figure 1. The Warbird SoC

considered in this study. After weighing few alternatives, the RISC-V's Rocket Chip generator was clearly the most advantageous choice.

This paper presents Warbird, the example SoC shown in Fig. 1. This SoC is the default configuration provided by Rocket Chip for FPGAs but, unlike the out of the box offer, Warbird is totally independent from the Xilinx FPGA Zynq processing System to operate. It uses its own a JTAG tap attached to the RISC-V debug module, which is instantiated in the Warbird design. The JTAG tap external pins are in fact connected to the FPGA pins, which are in turn connected to the GPIO pins of a USB device, the FT4322H mini module [9]. This device is then managed by the popular Open On Chip Debugger tool [10, 11] known as OpenOCD, which accepts connections over TCP/IP from different clients, among which is the very well known GNU Debugger (GDB) [12] tool.

Warbird features a simple memory mapped IO; in this first implementation only a scratch memory is connected to the IO system, but this is enough to test the IO read and write capabilities of the SoC. According to the target application, peripherals may be added or removed, which also means the addition or removal of their respective software drivers.

2.1. Rocket Processor and Co-Processor

The Rocket processor is a 5-stage in-order RISC-V processor. Rocket is equipped with instruction and data caches of configurable size, associativities and replacement policies, as well as instruction and data MMUs. It supports integer operations and optionally floating-point operations (where its pipeline stages can be configured). Branch prediction is configurable and it supports branch target buffer (BTB), branch history table (BHT), and a return address stack (RAS). Interrupts and exceptions of various types are also catered for. The Rocket is master of the system's AXI4 Crossbar bus, where many slave peripherals can be attached.

Rocket has an interface for co-processor communication. To make use of the co-processor(s) the RISC-V ISA can be extended with new instructions. The co-processor(s) can operate over virtual memory and has access to Rocket's

data cache and page walker, it can also interrupt the core. Furthermore, the co-processor(s) can connect directly to external memory allowing it to have a private cache system.

2.2. Boot ROM

After reset, the processor executes code permanently stored in a Boot ROM. This code typically loads a program stored in a non-volatile memory into the central memory. The Boot ROM is an AXI4 Crossbar slave.

2.3. DRAM controller

The RAM controller is the interface to an external central memory which is normally a single or double data rate (DDR) DRAM. Newer generations of DDRs, such as DDR3 or DDR4, can achieve better performance and higher density in terms of stored bits per unit of area. The DRAM controller is an AXI4 Crossbar slave.

The Rocket Chip infrastructure comes with no DRAM controller. A simulation model of the DDR is used and, when implemented in FPGA, the DDR controllers available in the device are used.

2.4. JTAG

The interface for loading and debugging programs is the 4-pin JTAG interface. The JTAG pins are connected to the JTAG tap module in the SoC, responsible for implementing the JTAG protocol. The 4 JTAG pins are connected to an external pod, which in turn connects to a host computer using, for example, USB or Ethernet.

The host computer may run the program loader or debugger, or it can simply act as a proxy for another computer where these client programs (loader or debugger) may be run. A debugger program could also run locally on the Rocket processor but, as the memory space for storing programs is a scarce resource, a remote debugger is preferred for embedded systems.

2.5. Debug module

The debug module sits between the JTAG tap and the AXI4 Crossbar bus of which it is a master. It also has a direct interface to the Rocket system in order to monitor and control its execution. Being the second master of the AXI4 Crossbar bus (Rocket is the first), the Debug module can read or write the central memory, which is useful for setting up soft breakpoints, access variables and other debug tasks.

3. SoC verification

A processor-based system is a complex system where no exhaustive testing can be guaranteed. At best, the system is exercised in as many ways as possible, trying to replicate real situations and to stress critical design corners. No one-size-fits-all solution exists and a combination of tech-

Figure 2. Verification environment.

niques is often employed. The verification environment for the Warbird SoC is illustrated in Fig. 2 and comprises two SoC verification methods: RTL simulation and FPGA emulation.

3.1. Test program and OpenOCD

Common to the two verification methods is the use of a C++ test bench (Test Program) and the universal chip debug tool called OpenOCD [10, 11]. Using a C++ test bench provides great flexibility in generating test stimuli for the Device Under Test (DUT) and checking its responses. OpenOCD provides a unified target access mechanism with pre-built configurations supporting many commercial development platforms, boards and interface media.

The Test Program communicates with OpenOCD using a networked socket to send OpenOCD commands. A simple Test Program is, for instance, a Telnet client where some target specific commands are manually issued, including commands for loading the program, starting and halting execution, etc.

With OpenOCD, the same Test Program can seamlessly exercise the two types of targets discussed: RTL simulation and FPGA emulation. A GDB client can also connect to OpenOCD for program debugging: the user sets a remote target using a specific OpenOCD port; henceforth, all GDB functionalities can be used to debug remote embedded programs as if they were local (for further details see section 4.2).

3.2. Verilog versus C++ RTL simulation

Verilog RTL simulation is the most commonly used method for SoC verification due to its accuracy, both in terms of timing and electrical behavior. Timing accuracy is obtained via event driven simulation, where component

delays dictate the instants when the circuit is re-evaluated. Electrical behavior is modeled by multi-valued logic: not only 0 and 1 states can be modeled but also other states such as X (0/1 conflict), U (unknown) and Z (high-impedance). The most used language in the industry for RTL design and verification is the Verilog language.

However, Verilog RTL simulation can be slow if applied to large logic circuits such as CPUs. It is an indispensable tool to verify the design though. Its level of detail is adequate even for the asynchronous parts of the design, namely clock domain crossings. Simulating systems where most interactions are software driven requires a considerable amount of stimulus data and verification of the response data. Writing such test benches in Verilog is hard and tedious. To solve this problem, a Verilog Procedural Interface (VPI) is normally employed. The VPI is a bridge between the test bench and an external C/C++ program, which actually does the complex stimuli generation and response analysis, reducing the test bench to the role of a mere proxy. The VPI method is better than pure Verilog RTL simulation but it is still difficult to set up requiring much accessory code to be written.

The large time taken by RTL simulations can become a bottleneck in the project schedule. As such, Embedded System Level (ESL) approaches have taken off in recent years to allow rapid design and verification of complex SoCs. Among such approaches, the SystemC initiative is one of the most prominent ones [13]. SystemC is a set of C++ libraries, containing classes and methods for designing and verifying digital circuits and systems.

A C++ model of the design is obtained from the design's Verilog description by running a free and open source tool called Verilator (verilated design). Simulation of this model can be faster than Verilog simulation but its time resolution and signal representation accuracy is lower, supporting only 2-valued logic ('0' and '1'). The C++ model created by Verilator can then be used as a class in C++ or SystemC test benches. The Warpbird simulation environment consists of the verilated design and a test bench written in C++. Integration with SystemC is under way. When compiled, these files produce a software emulator program, which communicates with the OpenOCD gateway using a TCP/IP socket.

Rocket Chip offers a testing framework called Torture for random program testing [14] which uses both RTL simulation and ISA simulation via the Spike simulator [15]. Torture generates RISC-V programs from small pieces of code and glues them together. At the end of each test, Torture dumps Rocket's registers from RTL simulation and compares them to simulation results of the same program in Spike [15]. If Torture finds an error in the core it will look for the smallest piece of code in the generated program which creates the error and stores it. The user can then use Torture's logs to debug the SoC.

3.3. FPGA emulation

Often one would like to test the actual SoC even before it is available in silicon. One of the best alternatives is to

use a circuit emulator, which is normally implemented with FPGA chips. Emulation provides the fastest verification method and, for circuits intended to run at low frequencies, emulation can even be real-time. As a reference, emulation speeds can be 1 to 2 orders of magnitude slower than real-time for complex SoCs implemented in the latest and densest IC technology nodes.

In spite of its performance, emulation provides poor visibility into the design's internal signals. When a bug is found, the designer first tries to diagnose the problem using software methods and/or logic analyzers to observe the interface signals. If observation of the interface signals is not sufficient, internal signals can be observed in the FPGA, with certain limitations, using an Integrated Logic Analyzer (ILA). The main limitations of ILAs are the maximum sampling frequency, the number and complexity of triggers, and the maximum amount of internal SRAM that can be used to store signals for observation.

4. Toolchain

The RISC-V SoC has a fully operational toolchain for barebone applications¹. Compilation, debugging and profiling are based on the corresponding GNU tools. Most of the tools available for RISC-V are already mature, and most have been merged upstream (their status is available in [16]).

A similar toolchain for Linux is also available, built with Newlib and a proxy kernel [17]. The latter is the basis for the Linux RISC-V port. There are also efforts to port other compilers and runtime environments, *e.g.*, OpenJDK, Go, Rust and OCaml.

4.1. Cross-compiler

The main barebone cross-compiler used for RISC-V is GCC and clang/LLVM. Although an LLVM/clang based version also exists, GCC is still needed to assemble and link the binary. The official GCC distribution supports RISC-V as of version 7.1.

Many cross-compilers available for commercial processors are built around GCC but, without violating its GNU General Public License (GPL), include closed static libraries for many key functionalities, namely architectural simulation, IO, target loading and debugger connectivity. One might be tempted to develop clean room interface compatible processors, lured by the availability of GCC and other GNU tools. This is a mistake, as the closed components may be very hard to develop, even though they represent a small part of the whole.

The RISC-V cross-compiler uses Newlib and is 100% open source, allowing for customization and tweaking. This possibility makes a huge difference for the developer, who can reflect hardware changes on the cross-compiler, perhaps not trivially, but for sure without any kind of reverse engineering. Hardware changes may affect the com-

¹A barebone application runs directly on the machine, without any operating system, and must *know* the underlying hardware.

mand line options of the cross-compiler to select particular configurations of the CPU and SoC. There are options to make the compilation aware of the floating-point unit, multiplication and division units, the clock frequency for a specific board, etc.

4.2. Debugger

The GNU debugger (GDB) is also available for the RISC-V SoC, and patches have already been submitted upstream. GDB provides an extensive range of facilities for execution tracing, halting on conditions, variable watching, etc. Usually run as a standalone application to debug local programs, GDB can also be run as a client/server application to debug a program in a remote system. The control of the target is left to a server which is accessed by the client via the `target remote` command. The client/server communication is done over TCP/IP and uses GDB's Remote Server Protocol (RSP).

The RSP server may run on the target system or on any machine that has some means of talking to the target. In our design, the RSP server runs within OpenOCD which, in turn, communicates via USB/JTAG with the target and acts as a GDB proxy server. The GDB client need not be on the same machine; for it, this process is transparent and everything works as if the GDB server was running on the target. The RISC-V debug specification has not been finalized and consequently the Debug Module does yet not support all OpenOCD features (at the time of this writing the debug specification is at version 0.13 [18]).

4.3. Chisel3

One of the biggest advantages of the Rocket Chip framework is the use of a novel hardware description language, Chisel [3]. Chisel was born out of a need to write hardware descriptions using powerful abstractions present in modern software languages.

Chisel3 is built on top of Scala [19], a Java-like language with support for functional programming and a static type system. From a top down view Chisel3 is a Verilog macro engine, *i.e.*, it generates a hardware description by composing pre-stored and small Verilog code snippets. Furthermore, Chisel3 features a standard library with components used in most hardware designs: single and double precision floating-point units, ROMs, RAMs, decoders, ripple-carry adders, booth multipliers, iterative dividers, etc. Chisel3 is able to generate Verilog optimized for FPGA or ASIC.

Abstraction within Chisel is an important aspect of the language, as it allows the hardware description to be parameterized, generic, and reusable. Another important aspect is the usage of generators. Generating several instances of the same component with different parameterizations and connections, or recursive connections is impossible in VHDL or Verilog without rewriting a large portion of code. Often a designer would have to use a Python script to recursively generate the correct hardware description.

Chisel3 offers a testing environment which is described in Chisel to test designs. There are two simulation targets,

Figure 3. Development flow.

a Chisel specific C++ RTL simulator or a Verilator target.

5. Development flow

The proposed SoC development flow is outlined in Fig. 3. It follows four distinct stages, each with several iterations between development and testing. Given the usual complexity, tests are seldom comprehensive: stepping back to prior stages and finding some previously uncaught issues is quite common.

5.1. Installation

The Warpbird SoC specific deliverables are packaged in several containers: hardware (Chisel3), RISC-V tools (spike, proxy kernel, OpenOCD), GNU toolchain (GCC, GDB) and test environment (Torture, SoC emulator). But in order to have a fully operational environment, some other tools must also be installed and/or configured, namely an RTL simulator like Verilator and Chisel3 (Scala environment and a couple of packages). After downloading Rocket Chip, setting the development environment is as easy as running a build script, and following the instructions to install Scala on your system.

The installation proved successful on Debian Linux (stable version Stretch) and on macOS High Sierra (version 10.13.1).

5.2. Peripherals

Once the development environment is successfully built and tested, the hardware customization phase may begin: adding or removing modules from the Rocket core, configuring peripherals for the SoC, or developing new peripherals suited for the aimed application. This phase includes writing and/or rewriting Chisel3 descriptions, but also entails the upgrading of the test bench, both for its hardware and software components.

The toolchain must be adapted to the new hardware, either via the available options mentioned in section 4.1, or via specific backend configuration files. When new peripherals are developed, the compiler backend may also need to be changed to accommodate the new functionalities.

The added functionalities may bring counterparts to the programming environment, namely by the creation of new software libraries. In that case, the test bench also needs to encompass those changes: programs using the new functions should be written and tested.

5.3. Application

The software application is developed in any favored IDE — an IDE integration is not provided. There are two straightforward ways of running and debugging the application, each with its own advantages and disadvantages: Spike, RTL software emulation and the FPGA SoC emulation.

Application testing with Spike has the advantage of running on the host computer, having no need for a board. However, the ISA simulator does not run as fast as the FPGA emulator and lacks some of the hardware features, namely the cache simulation. Running the application using the a software RTL emulator can simulate the system and all its peripherals at a cycle accurate level, but the simulation will be quite slow. As such, running the application on the FPGA is often necessary for speed and timing accuracy.

In any of the above scenarios, debugging of the target can be performed using the GDB client, as described in section 3.1, which is very convenient.

5.4. Optimization

The overall goal is to accelerate the application execution, which can be accurately measured using FPGA emulation even though, as mentioned in section 3.3, FPGA emulation is 1 to 2 orders of magnitude slower than real-time. There is no profiler available in the RISC-V toolchain. Currently, when compiling a program with the profiler option (`-pg`), GCC fails to link the binary against a library. Without the profiler, one may use a timer to measure the execution time of critical routines.

6. Conclusions and status

The Rocket Chip framework provides a strong basis for designing SoCs based on RISC-V cores, rendering the

whole effort orders of magnitude smaller than building hardware and software from scratch. This is the essence of a business model consisting of building original systems from open source components.

One major barrier to entering this market is the open source licensing model of the components. There is a lack of a standard license agreement for open source hardware descriptions [20], as most open source software licenses are not generally applicable. Most open source IP cores are made available using the GNU Lesser General Public License (LGPL), but adoption by users still lacks expression.

In this paper the focus is the construction of an untethered Rocket Chip instance called Warpbird, an SoC which can work independently and does not need to use any resources from its simulation environment, host FPGA or any external soft or hard IP block present in its packaging. The current Rocket Chip SoC generator uses resources from the Xilinx FPGA in which it is packaged, namely the ARM Cortex A9 processing system present in the Zynq devices, which is made responsible for program loading, control and IO, and does not have any debug infrastructure such as the Debug Module or the JTAG tap [21]. In contrast, Warpbird can be freely placed in any FPGA or ASIC, includes the Debug Module and the JTAG tap and has a detached memory mapped IO system. Program loading, control and debug are taken care of via JTAG and IO can be exemplified by just hanging a scratch memory from the IO bus. The building of Warpbird is an ongoing process. The status of the project as of December 2017 is reported in the following subsections.

6.1. Hardware status

The status of the Warpbird hardware components is summarized in Table 1. As indicated in this table, the FPGA hardware has been synthesized and implemented down to the bitstream, but it has not been brought up for testing.

Item	Comment
Rocket GPP	OK in RTL simulation; implemented but not yet run in FPGA.
Debug Module	OK in RTL simulation, implemented but not yet run in FPGA.
JTAG controller	OK in RTL simulation, implemented but not yet run in FPGA.
UART	Under Development.
I2C controller	Under Development.
SPI controller	Under Development.
DRAM controller	Non-existent, uses FPGA's or 3rd party.
Power Management Unit	Under Development.

Table 1. Warpbird FPGA hardware status

Using the ZedBoard platform [22], containing a Xilinx Zynq-7020-1 device [23], Warpbird, configured with

no floating-point unit, no branch prediction, no MMUs and with 16kB I/D caches, uses the resources shown in Table 2. These results confirm that Chisel3 is able to efficiently map a high level hardware description to all types of FPGA resources present in the device.

LUT	16037
LUTRAM	2256
Flip-Flops	6234
BRAM	4
Frequency	50MHz

Table 2. Warpbird Resource Usage in a Zynq-7020-1 device

Table 3 shows the resources used by the critical components in the Warpbird SoC. The results so far actually confirm that the open source IP cores behave well when ported to a user simulation environment.

Item	LUTs	BRAMs
RV64 core	3710	0
ICache	224	1.5
DCache	1418	1.5
Debug Module	1737	0

Table 3. Warpbird critical components resource usage

6.2. Verification status

The status of the verification components is summarized in Table 4. FPGA emulation and RTL simulation have been run as provided by Rocket Chip.

Item	Comment
Test program	Not started
OpenOCD	OK with RTL simulation
RTL simulation	Test suite and benchmarks pass
FPGA emulation	Only out of the box features tested, no test harness present yet.

Table 4. Verification status

6.3. Software status

The status of the software components is summarized in Table 5. In general, it can be said that these tools appear to be very mature, which aids the goals of the project.

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Item	Comment
GCC for C	Programs compiled correctly
GCC for C++	Simple programs compiled correctly
GDB	Tested with RTL and Spike; tests with FPGA emulation not started
Spike	Tested with simple programs
Profiler	Unavailable
Linux toolchain	Most of glibc has been ported
Linux OS	The provided kernel works as expected

Table 5. Software status

References

- [1] José T. de Sousa, Carlos A. Rodrigues, Nuno Barreiro, João C. Fernandes, “Building Reconfigurable Systems Using Open Source Components,” in *REC*, April 2014.
- [2] E. A. Waterman and K. Asanović, *The RISC-V Instruction Set Manual, Volume I: User-Level ISA, Document Version 2.2*, RISC-V Foundation, May 2017.
- [3] J. Bachrach, H. Vo, B. Richards, Y. Lee, A. Waterman, R. Avižienis, J. Wawrzynnek, and K. Asanović, “Chisel: Constructing hardware in a scala embedded language,” in *49th Design Automation Conference*, June 2012.
- [4] K. Asanović, R. Avižienis, J. Bachrach, S. Beamer, D. Biancolin, C. Celio, H. Cook, D. Dabbelt, J. Hauser, A. Izraelevitz, S. Karandikar, B. Keller, D. Kim, J. Koenig, Y. Lee, E. Love, M. Maas, A. Magyar, H. Mao, M. Moreto, A. Ou, D. A. Patterson, B. Richards, C. Schmidt, S. Twigg, H. Vo, and A. Waterman, “The rocket chip generator,” EECS Department, University of California, Berkeley, Tech. Rep. UCB/EECS-2016-17, Apr 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www2.eecs.berkeley.edu/Pubs/TechRpts/2016/EECS-2016-17.html>
- [5] Z. Stamenkovic, C. Wolf, G. Schoof, and J. Gaisler, “Leon-2: General purpose processor for a wireless engine.” in *DDECS*, M. S. Reorda, O. Novák, B. Straube, H. Kubatova, Z. Kotásek, P. Kubalík, R. Ubar, and J. Bucek, Eds. IEEE Computer Society, 2006, pp. 50–53. [Online]. Available: <http://dblp.uni-trier.de/db/conf/ddecs/ddecs2006.html#StamenkovicWSG06>
- [6] K. Horst, *Latticemico32*. Dign Press, 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://books.google.pt/books?id=LzGbMQEACAAJ>
- [7] O. community, “OpenRISC Reference Platform System-On-Chip,” 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/openrisc/orpsoc>
- [8] S. Craven, “The OpenFire Processor.” [Online]. Available: https://opencores.org/project.openfire_core
- [9] *FT4232H Mini Module, USB Hi-Speed FT4232H Evaluation*, Future Technology Devices International Ltd., Aug. 2009, version 1.5.
- [10] D. Rath, “Open On-Chip Debugger,” Jul. 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://openocd.org/files/thesis.pdf>
- [11] “OpenOCD — Open On-Chip Debugger,” 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://openocd.sourceforge.net>
- [12] R. Stallman, *GDB manual: the GNU source-level debugger*, 2nd ed., Free Software Foundation, Inc., Cambridge Mass., Feb. 1988.

- [13] "Ieee standard for standard systemc language reference manual," *IEEE Std 1666-2011 (Revision of IEEE Std 1666-2005)*, pp. 1–638, Jan 2012.
- [14] Y. Lee and H. Cook, "RISC-V Torture Test Generator," 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ucb-bar/riscv-torture>
- [15] A. Waterman and Y. Lee, "RISC-V ISA Simulator," 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/riscv/riscv-isa-sim>
- [16] R.-V. Foundation, "RISC-V Software Ecosystem Overview." [Online]. Available: <https://riscv.org/software-status/>
- [17] —, "RISC-V Proxy Kernel and Boot Loader." [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/riscv/riscv-pk>
- [18] T. Newsome, "RISC-V External Debug Support," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://static.dev.sifive.com/riscv-debug-spec-0.13.f7f3277.pdf>
- [19] M. Odersky, "Scala programming language." [Online]. Available: <http://www.scala-lang.org/>
- [20] E. Greenbaum, "Open source semiconductor core licensing," *Harv. JL & Tech.*, vol. 25, p. 131, 2011.
- [21] U. B. A. Research, "Rocket Chip on Zynq FPGAs," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ucb-bar/fpga-zynq>
- [22] "Zeadboard," 2017. [Online]. Available: http://zedboard.org/sites/default/files/product_briefs/5066-PB-AES-Z7EV-7Z020-G-V1b.pdf
- [23] "Zynq-7000 All Programmable SoC Data Sheet: Overview," June 2017. [Online]. Available: http://www.xilinx.com/support/documentation/data_sheets/ds190-Zynq-7000-Overview.pdf